

21NRM06 EMC-STD

D6: Report on the new alternative reference waveform with a commercial arbitrary waveform generator for calibration of measuring receivers to include a well-defined mathematical description and spectral properties for inclusion in standards as a means of validating the weighting function of the detectors and capable of reducing the uncertainty of the receiver's response to pulses calibration to 0.2 dB. This report will include a comparison with the traditional pulse generator calibration method. This report to be submitted to CISPR/CIS/AWG1 & WG2.

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Abbreviations

ADC	Analog-to-digital converter
AWG	Arbitrary Waveform Generator
CW	Continuous Wave
DAC	Digital-to-analog converter
DFT	Discrete Fourier transform
EM	Electromagnetic
EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
EMI	Electromagnetic Interference
EUT	Equipment under test
FD	Frequency domain
FFT	Fast Fourier transform
OL	Overlap factor
RTSA	Real time spectrum analyzer
STFT	Short-time Fourier transform
TD	Time-domain
TD-EMI	EMI receiver working in time-domain
WL	Window length

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Executive summary

This document reports the calibration of measuring receivers using new alternative reference waveforms with a commercial arbitrary waveform generator instead of a traditional base-band pulse generator or pulse-modulated CW generator, as recommended in CISPR 16-1-1 ed. 4. The reference waveforms are well defined and mathematically described so that they can be reproduced in commercial arbitrary waveform generators leading to known and repeatable spectral properties. The calibration using reproducible waveforms aims to reduce the uncertainty of the receiver's response to pulses calibration to 0.2 dB. This report includes a comparison with the traditional pulse-modulated CW generator calibration method.

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1. Introduction

The measuring receiver is a fundamental element in conducted and radiated electromagnetic emissions testing. Accordingly, the standard definition given in the CISPR 16-1-1 Ed. 4.0 [CISPR16-1-1] states it is an "instrument such as a tunable voltmeter, an electromagnetic interference receiver, a spectrum analyzer, or a fast Fourier transform (FFT)-based measuring instrument, with or without preselection, that meets the relevant parts of this standard" [CISPR16-1-1]. Henceforth, the standard CISPR 16-1-1 does not provide guidelines for any implementation of a measuring receiver but several requirements that the measuring instrument must fulfil under a "black-box" approach. In particular, the baseline (minimum) requirements that should be ensured for any measuring receiver are given in terms of four parameters, namely, voltage standing wave ratio, sine wave voltage accuracy, response to pulses, and selectivity [CISPR16-1-1].

Ensuring the measuring receiver complies with the specifications in CISPR 16-1-1 is mandatory. This is achieved through traceable calibration of the instrument regarding its standard requirements. Incidentally, the receiver's response to pulses of the weighting detectors is the most challenging aspect that must be calibrated. The calibration method requires generating broadband pulses with a given impulse area at specific repetition frequencies. Such pulses must deliver a known quasi-peak level and have a flat spectrum over the frequency band under consideration. Although the standard states the tolerable uncertainties for the pulse characteristics, it does not stipulate their exact waveform. In this report, it will be shown that other methods of EMI receiver calibration are possible apart from those recommended in [CISPR16-1-1].

2. Calibration of the response to pulses of EMI receivers

In the current version of CISPR 16-1-1 [CISPR16-1-1], the requirements given regarding the calibration pulses are limited to their amplitude level, frequency flatness (spectrum uniformity), impulse area, and pulse repetition frequency. The reference pulses' spectrum must be flat in the frequency band under assessment (CISPR bands A, B, and C/D) with a level equivalent to a tone having an RMS voltage of 2 mV, which means 66 dB(μ V) at 50 Ω source impedance and in open-circuit conditions. In this regard, the spectrum of the pulses is considered sufficiently flat if the deviation of the spectrum amplitude is less than ± 2 dB relative to its value for the lower frequencies within the band. For the absolute calibration of amplitude response, generally a signal with a uniform spectrum from the pulse generator is needed (at least in the bandwidth of the receiver). For the relative calibration of amplitude response, the exact value of the spectrum amplitude is not needed. However, the shape of the pulse must not change, and the pulse repetition rate must be stable. The following sections detail the calibration methods for EMI receivers.

2.1 Traditional EMI receiver calibration methods

The standard CISPR 16-1-1 [CISPR16-1-1] describes the calibration of an EMI receiver, either using base-band pulse generators or pulse-modulated CW generators. For calibrating the response to pulses of the weighting detectors, the established method involves using a baseband (nanosecond) pulse generator capable of delivering a set of pulses with a fixed impulse area and repetition frequency [Drosd1956]. Currently, to the best of the authors' knowledge, Schwarzbeck is the only manufacturer that provides specific pulse generators as a commercial solution for fulfilling CISPR 16-1-1 calibration requirements. This means the pulse generators IGUU 2916 and IGUU 2918 are both considered, by default, the sole standard for the calibration of the receivers' pulse response. This factual situation could be attributed to the ill-defined waveform characteristics of the reference pulses, and it contradicts, to some extent, the spirit of CISPR 16-1-1 annex K [CISPR16-1-1]. The calibration of pulse generators is generally not easy, as they produce large amplitudes (tens to hundreds of volts) and have fast edges. In the standard [CISPR16-1-1], only a very brief description of calibration methods of pulse generators is given, and technical details are hidden. The measurement uncertainty of the pulse generator characterization is not discussed in the standards. The detailed analysis of metrological characterization of pulse generators is given, e.g. in [Hudlicka2020]. The pulse generators are suitable for

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calibration of EMI receivers equipped with a preselector stage; otherwise, the energy in the pulses is too large and may be harmful to the receiver. Another method is the pulse-modulated CW signal, which has the energy distributed in a narrow band around the carrier frequency. The typical spectrum of a base-band pulse generator is given in Fig. 1. The pulse-modulated RF generator uses a harmonic signal with a pulse envelope. The spectrum is similar to a rectangular pulse (upconverted to the carrier frequency f_c), with the maximum of the spectrum at f_c . The spectrum is uniform in a given bandwidth, which implies that pulses with longer duration can be used with lower amplitudes compared to base-band pulse generators (lower risk of measuring receiver damage). The time-domain signal and its spectrum are schematically shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1 Typical spectrum of a rectangular pulse.

Fig. 2 Pulse-modulated RF signal in the time domain (left) and in the frequency domain (right).

2.2 Alternative calibration waveforms

In the paper [Azpurua2019], the characteristics of the CISPR 16-1-1 calibration pulses from a commercial Schwarzbeck IGUU2916 generator were studied, and a parametric model for describing waveforms compliant with the requirements was proposed. Those waveforms were numerically solved and evaluated for producing a reference voltage vector that can be synthesized using arbitrary function generators (AWG). The validity of the proposed waveforms was experimentally verified and compared with the waveforms produced by a commercial EMI calibration pulse generator. The artificially generated calibration pulses based on [Azpurua2019] fulfil all these requirements, provided a quality AWG is used. The main requirements of the pulse properties are given in Table 1.

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Table 1 Response to pulses (absolute calibration)

Band	A	B	C	D
Freq. range	{9 - 150} kHz	{0.15 - 30} MHz	{30 - 300} MHz	{300 - 1000} MHz
Impulse area (open-circuit)	13.5 μ Vs	0.316 μ Vs	0.044 μ Vs	0.044 μ Vs
Repetition rate	25 Hz	100 Hz	100 Hz	100 Hz

The pulse shape of the IGUU2616 pulse generator, measured using a fast real-time oscilloscope [Azpurua2019], is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Calibration pulse generated by the IGUU 2916 for CISPR band A (a), B (b), C/D (c).

Fig. 4 Generic representation of a trapezoid pulse

For defining the suitable waveforms for the measuring receivers' calibration pulses, let's start from the model of a periodic trapezoid pulse, $p(t)$, shown in Fig. 4. First, the amplitude of the trapezoid can be easily computed from the pulse area requirement, A_{imp} , and the pulsewidth, τ , as(1)

$$p(t) = c_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |c_n| \cos(n\omega_{rep}t + \theta_n), \quad (1)$$

where $\omega_{rep} = 2\pi f_{rep}$. The constant coefficient, c_0 , corresponds to the average value of the waveform over one period of time, that is

$$c_0 = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T p(t) dt = \frac{U\tau}{T}, \quad (2)$$

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whereas the magnitude and phase of the harmonic components of the Fourier series are given by

$$c_n = \frac{2}{T} \int_0^T p(t) e^{-in\omega_{rep}t} dt. \quad (3)$$

If (3) is solved for the case in which $t_r = t_f$, then the expressions for the amplitude and the phase of c_n are as follows:

$$|c_n| = 2U \frac{\tau}{T} \left(\frac{\sin(\pi n f_{rep} t_r)}{\pi n f_{rep} t_r} \right) \left(\frac{\sin(\pi n f_{rep} \tau)}{\pi n f_{rep} \tau} \right), \quad (4)$$

$$\theta_n = -\pi n (\tau + t_r) f_{rep}. \quad (5)$$

Then, for each CISPR band, there are a pair of coefficients c_l and c_u corresponding to the lower and upper frequency components of that band, f_l and f_u , respectively, where $l = f_l/f_{rep}$ and $u = f_u/f_{rep}$. For limiting the bandwidth of the calibration pulses, the amplitude of their spectrum must decrease with frequency above the upper limit of the frequency band. A certain decay (10 dB) in the pulse spectrum amplitude is expected at $2f_u$ to ensure consistent severity in terms of the influence of the receiver intermodulation products. Similarly, the DC and the frequency components above $2f_u$ can be discarded, as their energy contributions to the waveform are negligible. Consequently, the expression of the pulse calibration waveform, $p_{cal}(t)$, is given by

$$p_{cal}(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{2u} d_n |c_n| \cos(n\omega_{rep}t + \theta_n), \quad (6)$$

where d_n is the weighting factor for adjusting the amplitude of the n -th harmonic components, and it is defined by

$$d_n = 1 \quad \text{if } 1 \leq n \leq u, \\ d_n = \frac{D(nf_{ref})}{|c_n|} \quad \text{if } |n| > u, \quad (7)$$

where $D(f)$ is the decay function that describes the transition between the passband and the stopband regions of a zero-phase low-pass filter of unitary gain. In this regard, the abovementioned transition must be continuous, that is, $D(f_u) = |c_u|$. Additionally, it is known that at $f = 2f_u$ the amplitude of the pulse spectrum must be attenuated by a factor $\alpha \approx 0.316$ with respect to the level at the lower limit of the frequency band, which means, $D(2f_u) = \alpha |c_u|$. Finally, even if $D(f)$ is not specified, a linear relationship can be assumed for the sake of simplicity. Then, $D(f)$ is given by

$$D(f) = |c_u| + (\alpha |c_l| - |c_u|) \left(\frac{f}{f_u} - 1 \right). \quad (8)$$

Detailed numerical validation with regards to the spectral flatness and achieved spectrum amplitude was performed in [Azpurua2019].

2.3 Generating alternative waveforms

For the calibration of an EMI receiver, the waveforms of calibration pulses in bands A, B, C/D have been generated using MATLAB environment with settings according to Table 2 for all repetition rates in particular CISPR bands, i.e., $f_{rep} = \{100, 60, 25, 10, 5, 2, 1\}$ Hz for Band A and $f_{rep} = \{1000, 100, 20, 10, 2, 1\}$ Hz for Bands B and C/D, respectively.

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Table 2 Solution for the calibration pulse parameters

Parameter	CISPR Band		
	A	B	C/D
Amplitude of the trapezoid, U (open circuit)	7.14 V	33.50 V	146.67 V
Rise time of the trapezoid, t_r	1 μ s	5 ns	0.1 ns
Pulse width, τ	1.89 μ s	9.43 ns	0.3 ns

The number of samples for each waveform corresponds to the pulse repetition rate and sampling rate. The minimum sample rate for a successful waveform reconstruction in an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) is at least twice ($m = 2$) the highest frequency, i.e. frequency f_u . Finally, a higher oversampling rate was used to generate pulses in particular bands, i.e. $T_s = 1/(m \cdot f_u)$, see the overview in Table 3. For low repetition rates (f_{rep}) in Band C/D, the number of samples is rather high even for the minimum practical oversampling factor $N = 3$.

Table 3 Number of samples of the calibration pulse generated in different CISPR bands

CISPR band	f_u (MHz)	f_{rep} (Hz)	m	T_s (s)	# of samples
A	0.15	100	20	$3.33 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$3.00 \cdot 10^4$
		60			$5.00 \cdot 10^4$
		25			$1.20 \cdot 10^5$
		10			$3.00 \cdot 10^5$
		5			$6.00 \cdot 10^5$
		2			$1.50 \cdot 10^6$
		1			$3.00 \cdot 10^6$
B	30	1000	5	$6.667 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$1.50 \cdot 10^5$
		100			$1.50 \cdot 10^6$
		20			$7.50 \cdot 10^6$
		10			$1.50 \cdot 10^7$
		2			$7.50 \cdot 10^7$
		1			$1.50 \cdot 10^8$
C/D	1000	1000	3	$3.33 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$3.00 \cdot 10^6$
		100			$3.00 \cdot 10^7$
		20			$1.50 \cdot 10^8$
		10			$3.00 \cdot 10^8$
		2			$1.50 \cdot 10^9$
		1			$3.00 \cdot 10^9$

The generator used for experiments was Keysight 33622A, the main specifications are summarized in Table 4. The number of samples may be a limiting factor for uploading the waveform into an arbitrary waveform generator. As can be seen from Table 3, all waveforms from Band A fit into the generator's internal memory. For Band B, only the waveform for $f_{rep} = 1000$ Hz and 100 Hz fits into the memory, and for Band C/D, only the waveform for $f_{rep} = 1000$ Hz can be played using this particular waveform generator. The output amplitude scale 10 V (which means ± 5 V) is sufficient for Band A only (pulse amplitude 7.14 V into open circuit, i.e. 3.57 V into 50 Ω load, see Table 2). The pulses for Band B and Band C/D would require another generator with a larger output voltage. Using an amplifier might be a solution; however, power amplifiers usually distort the signal, leading to worse flatness in the spectrum amplitude.

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Table 4 Main specifications of the Keysight 33622A generator

Parameter	Value
Total harmonic distortion	0.03 %
Bandwidth	120 MHz
Sample memory length	64 MSa
Output amplitude (peak-peak)	10 V up to 60 MHz into a 50 Ω load
Voltage resolution	14 bits
DC Offset	± (5 V - Peak AC) into 50 Ω

The Keysight 33622A generator voltage resolution 14 bits and total harmonic distortion 0.03 % make the output waveform almost perfect. Any potential deviation from the calculated waveform cannot be easily identified using an oscilloscope (typical vertical resolution 12-14 bits in Band A and B and 10-12 bits in Band C/D) or EMI receiver. The influence of the limited DAC resolution (number of bits) of the AWG was studied numerically, see Fig. 5. The calculated spectral amplitude of the waveform discretized to $N = 8$ to $N = 14$ bits (corresponding to AWGs of various quality) is shown in Fig. 6. The error of spectral amplitude is negligible for $N = 10$ to $N = 14$ bits and is still reasonably low even for $N = 8$ bits of the generator DAC (such a low vertical DAC resolution can be found instead in AWGs with bandwidths > 5 GHz).

Fig. 5 Band A calibration pulse discretized to a different number of quantization levels (corresponding to N bits of the DAC); the main part of the calibration pulse (left) and the detail for better visibility of discretization levels.

Fig. 6 Spectral amplitude deviation from the theoretical value when using different discretization of the calibration pulse

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2.4 Calibration of EMI receivers using alternative waveforms

Two different EMI receivers have been calibrated using the alternative waveform (calibration pulse) discussed in previous sections: the R&S ESCS30 (frequency-domain receiver, heterodyne principle) and the PicoScope 5444D oscilloscope with emiGO software [emiGO] (oscilloscope bandwidth 200 MHz). Other alternative waveforms (e.g. multisine) have not been tried in this experiment. The waveforms have been uploaded to the AWG Keysight 33622A using the commercial software Keysight Benchlink Waveform Builder, which plays the waveform in an infinite loop at the signal output. The R&S ESCS30 has a 50 Ω input impedance; for the PicoScope 5444D, a feedthrough BNC 50 Ω load was used. The absolute and relative response to pulses of both EMI receivers was measured, and the results are given in Section 3. A photo of the measurement setup is shown in Fig. 7. The pulse waveform from the AWG was measured by both the FD (R&S ESCS30) and the TD (PicoScope 5444D + emiGO software) receivers.

Fig. 7 Photo of the measurement setup

The values from the PicoScope 5444D and the emiGO software were obtained using cursors; the values from the R&S ESCS30 were obtained from the instrument's display. An example of the emiGO screen is shown in Fig. 8 (frequency domain) and Fig. (time domain), with measurements into the oscilloscope's 1 MΩ input (mimicking an open-circuit measurement); for a 50 Ω input, the amplitudes are 3 dB lower.

Fig. 8 emiGO screenshot (frequency domain); PicoScope 5444D, Band A 9 kHz – 150 kHz, QP detector.

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Fig. emiGO screenshot (time domain); PicoScope 5444D, Band A 9 kHz – 150 kHz, QP detector, 10 pulses.

3. Measurement results

In this section, two different calibration methods will be shown on two different EMI receivers. The calibration methods are (i) a pulse-modulated CW signal and (ii) a calibration pulse described in Section 2.3. The EMI receivers are (i) an FD receiver R&S ESCS30, and (ii) an FD receiver PicoScope 5444D + emiGO software (only channel A of the oscilloscope was studied using the calibration pulse method).

3.1 Absolute sine level accuracy

A continuous sine-wave signal was generated using the R&S SMG generator and checked using a calibrated power sensor, R&S NRV-Z4, and a power meter, R&S NRVD. Several frequencies within Band A were chosen. The results for absolute sine level accuracy are shown in Table 5. The tolerance is ± 2 dB according to [CISPR16-1-1].

Table 5 Calibration results of the absolute sine level accuracy

frequency (kHz)	input level (dB μ V)	PicoScope 5444D			R&S ESCS30		
		meas. level (dB μ V)	unc. ($k=2$) (dB)	error (dB)	meas. level (dB μ V)	unc. ($k=2$) (dB)	error (dB)
10	66	66.024	0.090	0.024	65.87	0.10	-0.13
80	66	66.038	0.090	0.038	65.88	0.10	-0.12
149	66	66.084	0.090	0.084	65.92	0.10	-0.08

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3.2 Relative response to pulses

The relative response to pulses with different repetition rate f_{rep} was measured using the (i) pulse-modulated CW signal and (ii) alternative calibration pulse from Section 2.3. The tolerances from [CISPR16-1-1] are given in Table 6.

Table 6 Response to pulses (relative calibration)

f_{rep} (Hz)	Change of the input level with the change of repetition rate, resulting in a constant receiver indication (dB)			
	Band			
	A {9 - 150} kHz	B {0.15 - 30} MHz	C {30 - 300} MHz	D {300 - 1000} MHz
1000	-	-4.5 ± 1	-8 ± 1	-8 ± 1
100	-4 ± 1	0 (ref)	0 (ref)	0 (ref)
60	-3 ± 1	-	-	-
25	0 (ref)	-	-	-
20	-	6.5 ± 1	9 ± 1	9 ± 1
10	4 ± 1	10 ± 1.5	14 ± 1.5	14 ± 1.5
5	7.5 ± 1	-	-	-
2	13 ± 2	20.5 ± 2	26 ± 2	26 ± 2
1	17 ± 2	22.5 ± 2	28.5 ± 2	28.5 ± 2

Results of the relative response to pulses for both calibration methods are summarised in Table 7 (PicoScope 5444D + emiGO software) and Table 8 (R&S ESCS30).

Table 7 Relative response to pulses, PicoScope 5444D + emiGO software, $f = 100$ kHz, Band A (channel A of the oscilloscope)

f_{rep} (Hz)	Pulse-modulated CW signal		AWG calibration pulse	
	QP (dBuV)	QP rel. (dB)	QP (dBuV)	QP rel. (dB)
100	64.00	-4.01	63.40	-4.05
60	62.99	-3.00	62.30	-2.95
25	60.00	0 (ref.)	59.35	0 (ref.)
10	55.98	4.01	55.20	4.15
5	52.51	7.49	51.70	7.65
2	47.07	12.92	45.80	13.55

Table 8 Relative response to pulses, R&S ESCS30, $f = 100$ kHz, Band A

f_{rep} (Hz)	Pulse-modulated CW signal		AWG calibration pulse	
	QP (dBuV)	QP rel. (dB)	QP (dBuV)	QP rel. (dB)
100	63.7	-3.7	64	-4.1
60	62.6	-2.6	63.2	-3.3
25	60.0	0 (ref.)	59.9	0 (ref.)
10	56.0	4.0	55.5	4.4
5	52.1	7.9	52.1	7.8
2	46.3	13.7	46.3	13.6

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From Table 7 and Table 8, it can be seen that the measurement results of both methods (i.e. the traditional pulse-modulated CW signal and the alternative method using calibration pulse and AWG) are similar and both are within the specification of the CISPR 16-1-1 standard. The measurement setup for the pulse-modulated CW signal is shown in Fig. 9 (the RF generator for band C/D was not used during this experiment, as the PicoScope 5444D is not capable of measurement in CISPR bands C/D).

Fig. 9 Measurement setup for the pulse-modulated CW signal (measurement of relative response to pulses)

4. Measurement uncertainty

The measurement uncertainty of the response to pulses is detailed below for both calibration methods (i.e. the traditional pulse-modulated CW signal and the alternative method using a calibration pulse and an AWG).

4.1 Pulse-modulated CW signal

The method uses square-wave pulses to modulate a CW signal from an RF generator. The pulse is not ideal, i.e. it may contain small ringing in the beginning and end of the pulse and also the flatness of the pulse may not be ideal. The resulting impulse area is then influenced by these factors. The burst is almost ideal in Band A, whereas it is more distorted in Bands B and C/D (see Fig. 10). For each carrier frequency, a different number of periods of the CW signal is contained in the burst.

Fig. 10 Example of RF burst (pulse-modulated CW signal); ideal burst in band B, $f = 1$ MHz (left), real pulse in band B, $f = 50$ MHz (right)

The error of the quasi-peak reading is generally determined by the quasi-peak reading of the device under test, the CISPR receiver's resolution and accuracy, the accuracy of the reference impulse area of the signal, the power meter's accuracy, and the uncertainties of the modulation pulse repetition frequency and the RF pulse duration.

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$$E = P_x + c_{res} - P_{nom} - c_{imp} - c_{PRF}, \tag{9}$$

where

P_x = quaci-peak reading of the CISPR receiver

c_{res} = CISPR receiver display resolution

P_{nom} = nominal quasi-peak reading (60 dB(μV))

c_{imp} = deviation of the impulse area from ideal value (determined from the weighting curves given in [CISPR16-1-1], section 5.2.2)

c_{PRF} = correction factor due to the uncertainty of the pulse repetition frequency

The typical measurement uncertainty budget for the R&S ESCS30 EMI receiver is shown in Fig. 11. The most significant measurement uncertainty contribution here is the repeatability of the reading of the R&S ESCS30 receiver, which is approx. 0.2 dB taken from 5 measurements. For the PicoScope 5444D, the repeatability of the readings is excellent, with a value of <0.05 dB. Then the total measurement uncertainty of the error of the quasi-peak reading is below 0.2 dB. The term M describes the uncertainty due to impedance mismatch between the receiver and cable and the cable and generator.

$f =$	0.010 MHz	$P_{nom} =$	66 dBuV	$=$	-41 dBm		
				Γ_{SA}	0.090		
				Γ_{gen}	0.050		
				Γ_{cab}	0.050		
Quantity	Estimate	Estimate uncertainty	Probability distribution	Div.	Standard uncertainty	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution
X_i	x_i				$u(x_i)$	c_i	$u_i(y)$
P_x	63.70 dBuV	0.2000 dB	normal	1	0.2000 mW	1.0 dB	0.200 dB
c_{imp}	0.05 dB	0.10 dB	normal	1	0.1000 mW	-1.000 dB	-0.100 dB
c_{res}	0 dB	0.006 dB	rectangular	1.73	0.0035 mW	1.000 dB	0.003 dB
c_{clin}	0 dB	0.01 dB	rectangular	1.73	0.0058 mW	1.000 dB	0.006 dB
c_{PRF}	0 dB	0.005 dB	normal	1	0.0050 mW	-1.000 dB	-0.005 dB
P_{nom}	66.00 dBuV	0.0700 dB	normal	2	0.0350 mW	-1.0 dB	-0.035 dB
M_{sacab}	1	0.0090	U-shaped	1.41	0.0064	1.0	0.006 dB
M_{gencab}	1	0.0050	U-shaped	1.41	0.0035	1.0	0.004 dB
E	-2.350 dB		Standard Uncertainty of measurement:				0.227 dB
			Expanded uncertainty of measurement:				0.453 dB

Fig. 11 Measurement uncertainty budget for the measurement of pulse-modulated CW signal

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4.1 Calibration pulse method

The calibration pulse is generated using the AWG Keysight 33622A with excellent fidelity, and the pulse shape is almost identical to the mathematical model. The cable from the AWG to the EMI receiver adds an additional 0.05 dB level decrease due to the insertion loss at 100 kHz frequency. The AWG resolution 14 bits and harmonic distortion of the generated waveform are taken into account in terms C_{clin} and C_{cimp} . The input reflection coefficient of the PicoScope 5444D with a 50 Ω feedthrough load is generally worse than the R&S ESCS30 and is approximately $\Gamma = 0.1$ at 100 kHz. Other uncertainty components are the same as for the previous method. The typical measurement uncertainty budget when using the PicoScope 5444D oscilloscope is shown in Fig. 12.

$f =$	0.010 MHz	$P_{nom} =$	66 dBuV	$=$	-41 dBm			
				Γ_{osc}	0.100			
				Γ_{gen}	0.060			
				Γ_{cab}	0.050			
Quantity	Estimate	Estimate uncertainty	Probability distribution	Div.	Standard uncertainty	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution	
X_i	x_i				$u(x_i)$	c_i	$u_i(y)$	
P_x	63.40 dBuV	0.0400 dB	normal	1	0.0400 mW	1.0 dB	0.040 dB	
c_{imp}	0.05 dB	0.05 dB	normal	1	0.0500 mW	-1.000 dB	-0.050 dB	
c_{res}	0 dB	0.006 dB	rectangular	1.73	0.0035 mW	1.000 dB	0.003 dB	
c_{clin}	0 dB	0.01 dB	rectangular	1.73	0.0058 mW	1.000 dB	0.006 dB	
c_{PRF}	0 dB	0.002 dB	normal	1	0.0020 mW	-1.000 dB	-0.002 dB	
P_{nom}	66.00 dBuV	0.0700 dB	normal	2	0.0350 mW	-1.0 dB	-0.035 dB	
M_{osccab}	1	0.0120	U-shaped	1.41	0.0085	1.0	0.008 dB	
M_{gencab}	1	0.0060	U-shaped	1.41	0.0042	1.0	0.004 dB	
E	-2.650 dB		Standard Uncertainty of measurement:					0.074 dB
			Expanded uncertainty of measurement:					0.148 dB

Fig. 12 Measurement uncertainty budget for the measurement of the calibration pulse from AWG

5. Conclusion

The research conducted confirms that, as prior theoretical models suggested, multiple alternative reference waveforms can be validly used to calibrate the measuring receivers in accordance with CISPR 16-1-1.

One open question was whether arbitrary waveform generator technology could generate, with sufficient fidelity, the alternative waveforms proposed from a purely mathematical perspective. This hypothesis was confirmed experimentally and by numerical experiments. The immediate consequence is that measuring the receiver's response to pulses can be calibrated without necessarily using the de facto industrial reference generators from the IGUU series by Schwarzbeck.

Another important highlight is that, unlike with traditionally used pulse generators for calibrating measuring receivers, the alternative calibration methods recommended and validated in this work provide a complete description of the reference waveform in both the time and frequency domains. This improves the metrological traceability and provides a direct explanation of the calibration results.

Finally, it was shown that the receiver's response to pulse calibration method based on AWG and digitally synthesised waveforms delivered a measurement uncertainty of approximately ± 0.15 dB, which is ± 0.3 dB less than the one estimated for the pulse modulated CW method.

Overall, the research summarised in this report (D6) contributes to achieving this project's third objective.

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